

Distributed Task Scheduling in Collaborative Edge Infrastructures with Graph Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—The complexity of modern applications necessitates the decomposition of workloads into logically dependent subtasks. As infrastructures move closer to data sources to decongest backbone networks and reduce communication delays, task deployment and scheduling become increasingly challenging. Orchestrators must respect spatial and temporal dependencies among subtasks and computing nodes, while optimizing goals such as latency and energy consumption. As edge adoption remains limited, operators pursue cooperative solutions that share resources without requiring significant investment. We consider a collaborative infrastructure, split into multiple domains, each with proprietary resources, and a shared pool for all service demands. Multiple agents operate concurrently with partial knowledge of the system, cooperating to allocate shared resources efficiently. In this work, we propose a Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning scheduler that leverages Graph Neural Networks to handle spatiotemporal dependencies and uses lightweight inter-domain messaging for inter-domain cooperation. The learned policy is scalable and effective, reducing execution time and energy, increasing parallelism and mitigating congestion in simulations with real workload data.

Keywords—Task Scheduling, Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning, Graph Neural Networks, Edge Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the technological development and widespread adoption of intelligent devices have driven demand for increasingly complex applications [1]. The traditional model of rigid atomic tasks for user requests cannot keep up with the evolving use cases and their requirements. Consequently, modern workloads comprise jobs decomposed into subtasks with temporal and logical dependencies, modelled as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs). This decomposition enables greater parallelism among independent subtasks and thus improves scalability by breaking larger tasks into smaller units [2]. These benefits, however, come with added complexity for the schedulers, which must in addition to other constraints adhere to subtask dependency constraints while allocating resources across distributed machines.

This complexity is exacerbated by the adoption of edge computing. It complements the cloud by moving computing resources closer to data sources and integrating with existing infrastructure to decongest backbone networks and offers a low latency and energy efficient alternative. The result is a

dynamic and interconnected device-edge-cloud continuum that delivers shorter response times, and higher utilization with lower energy consumption [3]. In such distributed settings, effective orchestration and resource provisioning are paramount given the heterogeneous capabilities of the devices involved, further complicating DAG based task scheduling.

Despite its apparent benefits, edge adoption remains low [4]. Enterprises still rely on centralized cloud solutions for their operational needs citing high upfront costs and resource constraints [5]. Edge providers must be able to meet demand reliably, without overprovisioning idle infrastructure. This creates incentives for resource sharing and cooperative management, enabling access to adequate resources while maintaining sustainable operational costs. However, orchestrating cooperative infrastructures at scale and serving multiple entities while preserving their privacy and autonomy is challenging under partial observability, limited telemetry and non-stationary demands. These constraints motivate data-driven orchestration schemes capable of effective collaboration. In this context, Multi Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL) [6] is a promising approach, as it allows joint agent training for optimization of system-level goals through coordination with partial environment telemetry [7].

In this work, we integrate Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) [8] and MARL to enable cooperative, distributed, online task scheduling among heterogeneous devices. We propose an edge resource sharing framework that allows multiple entities to contribute a portion of their resources, forming a unified infrastructure capable of effectively meeting user demand. In this environment, multiple agents operate autonomously and concurrently with partial observability of each other's conditions to schedule incoming task requests, manage the shared resources, and optimize task latency and energy consumption. A novel GNN attention mechanism is introduced to jointly encode the task dependency DAG and the infrastructure graph, so the agent policy accounts for both workload and topology. Agents also exchange lightweight messages containing their local observations (e.g. proprietary resource utilization) to coordinate and avoid congestion.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II we report on the related work, Section III presents the problem and system model. In Section IV we formulate the problem as a Decentralized Partially Observable Markov Decision Process (Dec-POMDP) and describe the GNN-MARL task scheduling mechanism. Simulation results are presented in Section V, and the paper concludes in Section VI.

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II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we review the literature on distributed task scheduling, a topic that has recently gained significant attention due to the adoption and rise of edge computing.

Task scheduling methods can be distinguished by whether the considered tasks are atomic (single, monolithic jobs) or dependent, composed of interrelated subtasks. Scheduling the former involves the assignment of monolithic jobs to a single machine and targets high utilization with low execution time, power consumption and associated cost. The online version of the problem, with continuously arriving requests, has been extensively studied. Best-fit heuristic methods that account for multiple optimization criteria simultaneously with near optimal performance are among the most common techniques [9]. GNN models have also been employed [10] to interpret the infrastructure topology with promising results, while in [11] batches of requests are served in a static setting, solved using convex optimization techniques. Finally, as orchestration is becoming increasingly decentralized to reduce privacy risk and communication overheads, schedulers may operate under uncertainty and must coordinate resource access. To this end, the authors in [12] introduced Reinforcement Learning (RL) agents, trained with Federated Learning that choose between local and remote task execution, and allocate resources based on partial infrastructure.

As application size and complexity grow, the DAG task model has become predominant. Scheduling DAG tasks inherits the challenges of atomic tasks and adds the need to manage subtask interdependencies. Linear Programming has been used to find the optimal solution [13] with respect to end-to-end constraints, however, the problem's complexity and time sensitivity makes such methods inapplicable due to high computational overheads. Various RL methods have also been employed to produce reactive agents that handle assignment and scheduling. In [14] the authors, employ Temporal Difference Learning to approximate the value function with telemetry data across time as input, and outperform a game theoretic baseline. A distributed training framework for application placement using the IMPALA RL method in edge-cloud computing infrastructures was proposed in [15], surpassing greedy and standard RL baselines, while also speeding up convergence and decreasing training time. Despite these gains, standard Deep RL struggles with scalability as it requires extensive retraining in case the infrastructure or workload changes, leading to the use of techniques like padding that potentially skew its performance. Moreover, the relations between infrastructure nodes and within submitted tasks require advanced interpretation. Modified heuristics have been proposed in literature [16], but their ability to realize spatial and temporal dependencies is limited. For this reason, GNNs have been successfully employed as they specialize in processing graph structured data and can provide orchestrators and schedulers with useful insights. In [17] a pipeline is established with a Graph Convolution Network (GCN) extracting features from the dependency graph, which are then employed by an RL agent to produce a dependency-aware deployment scheme. The authors in [18] follow a similar approach, processing the dependency graph using a Graph Attention Network (GAT),

but also combining its output with a GCN that interprets the edge infrastructure, to produce a fully informed policy.

Orchestration must also adapt to rising security concerns and infrastructure heterogeneity as protocols, capabilities and concurrent entities overlap. Accordingly, methods operating under partial observability have been proposed, to enable cooperative resource management. In [19], MARL is combined with multi-agent Rollout to deliver a multi objective resource allocation mechanism for concurrent domains with limited inter-domain interaction. Similarly, the authors in [20] propose a MARL solution that delegates subtask processing decisions to the nodes, effectively distributing the orchestration process. However, the proposed mechanism assumes that each node has full observation of the environment. Our work instead proposes a distributed framework for scheduling DAG tasks, in which multiple agents coordinate over shared resources under partial knowledge of the underlying infrastructure, using a custom GNN model to interpret tasks inter-dependencies. This differentiates it from existing works, which either implement centralized orchestration with full infrastructure telemetry or fully decentralized orchestration with limited cooperation capabilities and security assurances.

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We assume a distributed infrastructure modeled as an undirected weighted graph $G = (V, E)$. Each node $u \in V$ denotes a compute location, while each edge $(u, u') \in E$ represents a communication link between two nodes u and u' , with the weight $w_{u,u'}$ indicating their communication latency. At each node $u \in V$, different types of computational resources can be deployed, ranging from specialized hardware to small-scale DCs. Hence, each node is characterized by the tuple $\tau_u = [f_u, s_u, p_u, b_u]$, where f_u is the available capacity in CPU cores, s_u is the node's computing speed coefficient s_u dependent on device type, p_u is the node's power consumption p_u measured in Watts and b_u is the available bandwidth for transmitting/receiving data, measured in bits/sec.

Multiple entities operate within the infrastructure, forming the set D of distinct domains each managed by its own scheduler. Schedulers aggregate task requests submitted by users within their domain and schedule the associated subtasks at the appropriate computing resources. Each domain $i \in D$

Fig. 1: Example of a simple task's assignment and scheduling.

has exclusive access to proprietary near edge resources, as well as to a shared pool of more powerful far edge resources, contributed by all entities and usable by all schedulers. Therefore, the compute resources accessible to domain i are represented by the subgraph $g_i \subset G$.

Time is divided into discrete windows of 1 time unit. Each task a represents a complete application (e.g. augmented reality, image generation) and can be decomposed into logically and temporally related subtasks that provide some intermediate function (e.g. data preprocessing, inference). The subtasks of task a form the DAG $G^a = (V^a, E^a)$ where the edges represent data dependencies between subtasks. Each subtask $m \in V^a$ has a computing requirement c_m based on its intensity, measured in the number of CPU cores required to process a bit. The arrival of user requests within each domain i is modelled as a Poisson process with a constant arrival rate λ_i . The amount of data d , measured in bits, to be processed for each request varies. Hence, request j sent to domain i at period t is characterized by the tuple $q_{j,i,t} = [d_{j,i,t}, a_{j,i,t}]$ containing the submitted data size and task structure.

We consider online task scheduling. The processing time of each subtask depends on its computational intensity, the data volume and the speed of the computing node to which it has been assigned by the scheduler. Specifically, the total processing time $T_{m,j,i,u}^P$ for subtask m of request j submitted to domain i at node u is provided below, adapted from [21]:

$$T_{m,j,i,u}^P = \frac{d_{j,i} \cdot c_m}{s_u} \quad (1)$$

For the specified time period, appropriate resources based on the subtask's intensity are reserved exclusively for its processing at the chosen device. Subtasks are executed in the order imposed by the task DAG representing and may run in parallel when independent (i.e., they do not have to exchange data). A subtask m assigned to node u that depends on the result of another subtask m' assigned to node u' , must wait for m' to finish and its data to be transferred from u to u' . The communication delay $T_{j,i,u,u'}^C$ for transferring the results of a subtask of request j in domain i from node u to node u' depends on transmitted data size, the nodes' link available bandwidth and their propagation delay $w_{u,u'}$, and is given by:

$$T_{j,i,u,u'}^C = \frac{d_{j,i}}{\min(b_u, b_{u'})} + w_{u,u'} \quad (2)$$

The processing of a subtask is also energy consuming. Assuming a per core power draw p_u at node u , the energy required to process subtask m of request j in domain i is proportional to its processing time and intensity:

$$E_{m,j,i,u} = T_{m,j,i,u}^P \cdot p_u \cdot c_m \quad (3)$$

We consider a task complete when its last subtask is finished, and the output is returned to the user. A scheduling example for a simple task request is presented in Fig. 1. It highlights a complete task, split into 5 subtasks, including logging, data preprocessing, authentication, model inference and database storage access. The scheduler maps each subtask to a device, subject to resource availability, resulting in an execution order that depends on data transmission delays, subtask processing times as well as interdependencies with independent subtasks potentially running in parallel.

IV. GRAPH MARL TASK SCHEDULING

The distributed nature of task scheduling in collaborative infrastructures requires each scheduler to act on partial system telemetry with decisions that may affect its peers. We thus model the problem as a Dec-POMDP to enable decentralized decision-making under partial observability and employ a GNN with a modified attention mechanism to fuse workload and topology information for coordination.

A. Dec-POMDP and MARL Formulation

A Dec-POMDP is defined by the tuple $\mathcal{M} = \{\mathcal{D}, S, \mathcal{A}, R, \Omega\}$, where \mathcal{D} is the finite set of agents, S is the state space, \mathcal{A} is the joint action space of all agents, R is the reward function, and $\Omega \subset S$ is the observable space for each agent. The Dec-POMDP components are described below:

Agent: Each domain's scheduler is treated as an agent; thus the agent set \mathcal{D} coincides with the domain set D , $\mathcal{D} \equiv D$. Agents interact with the environment in discrete time steps, choosing actions that alter the environment's state to maximize the cumulative reward over a full environment traversal (episode).

State and Observation: The environment comprises (i) the joint computing infrastructure with node characteristics for all domains and shared resources, (ii) users generating requests, and (iii) the schedulers (agents). Together these define the state space S . Each domain's agent observes the part of state space S it can access, i.e. the proprietary and shared resources' related telemetry and availability data, along with their domain's received requests. Given that agents share part of their resources, possibly leading to contention and congestion, they periodically exchange minimal messages with information about their observations (e.g., queue length, average subtask demand, current utilization) to their peers, facilitating resource management without compromising security. The observation of agent i at time t is the concatenation of local telemetry, its current request and peer messages ω_j by all domains $j \in D$, with their knowledge producing final observation $o_i \in \Omega \subset S$ for period t , shown below, with the \oplus symbol denoting concatenation:

$$o_i^t = \tau_{u \in g_i} \oplus q_{j,i,t} \oplus \omega_{i' \in D - \{i\}} \quad (4)$$

Action: At each decision step t , agent i selects a node from its action space \mathcal{A} to assign the current subtask of a given request. The agent then proceeds to the next subtask and moves to the next task request once all subtasks of the current one are scheduled. All agents' actions are aggregated in the joint action A^t , used to interact with the environment at step t :

$$A^t = [a_1^t, a_2^t, \dots, a_{|D|}^t] \quad (5)$$

The action space of an agent contains all feasible node options, based on their ownership status and resource availability. Action masking is used to obfuscate infeasible nodes and prevent their selection, ensuring the solution's viability.

Reward: The agents' objective is to learn a set of potential actions for each observation, namely a policy, i.e. a function that defines the probability distribution over actions, so that for observation $o \in \Omega$, $\pi(a|o)$ is the probability that the agent selects action a from the available actions, which would have the agent maximize the total sum of all rewards in an episode

[6]. In the examined case, our objectives are task execution time and energy consumption minimization. To this end, we structure the reward $r \in R$ to penalize agents for assignments that result in increases in the above metrics, by incorporating a negative weighted linear sum of said metrics:

$$r^t = -w_1 \cdot (T_{m,j,i,a}^P + T_{j,i,a',u'}^C) - w_2 \cdot E_{m,j,i,u} \quad (6)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weight coefficients for the task's execution time and power consumption respectively. As the agents' goal is the minimization of the aforementioned metrics to maximize the cumulative system reward, inter-agent cooperation is necessary. For this reason, the individual reward signal produced by each agent is combined with the normalized joint reward signal of all active agents, to convey the total system performance, using a chosen fraction $\xi \in [0,1]$. This combined reward is employed during training to create a parameterized reward that captures the effect of both individual action and the achieved global synergy.

$$r_{i,joint}^t = \xi \cdot r_i^t + (1 - \xi) \cdot \frac{1}{|D| - 1} \cdot \sum_{i' \in D - \{i\}} r_{i'}^t \quad (7)$$

B. GNN MARL Actor-Critic Framework

We solve the Dec-POMDP with Multi Agent Graph Reinforcement Learning. Multi-Agent Proximal Policy Optimization (MAPPO) [22] is employed to produce intelligent scheduling agents as it is a general purpose, policy-based algorithm. It relies on the clipped surrogate objective, a function used to stabilize training by capping policy updates and preventing new policies from deviating significantly from old ones. MAPPO utilizes Actor-Critic networks, with the Actor functioning as a policy estimator, continuously updating and learning a parameterized policy function π_θ that outputs a probability distribution over possible actions. Conversely, the Critic approximates the state value function $V_\pi(s)$, defined below as the expected cumulative reward starting at state s , following the current policy π until a terminal state is reached:

$$V_\pi(s) = \mathbb{E}_\pi \left[\sum_{k=0}^T \gamma^k R_{t+k+1} \mid S_t = s \right], \text{ for all } s \in S \quad (8)$$

where T is the episode duration and $\gamma \in (0,1)$ is a discount factor. Henceforth, the Critic estimates if an agent benefits by being in a particular state to assist with policy updates and

functions as a performance indicator. A centralized Critic is used in the training process to convey a better understanding of the global state to the Actors, according to the Centralized Training with Decentralized Execution (CTDE) paradigm.

Actor-Critic pairs typically employ Multi-Layer Perceptrons, which struggle in interpreting spatial relationships, including those present in interconnected infrastructures and dependent tasks. In our setting, an agents' action space comprises the potential computing nodes for assigning a subtask. We notice that the output of GNNs, which can provide a score for each node in a given input graph, is consistent with the desired output of the Actor network, when the given graph is the available infrastructure. Therefore, we employ GNNs to compute suitability scores (logits) for all infrastructure nodes, apply action masking to invalidate infeasible nodes, and convert the remaining logits to a probability distribution to obtain the policy function π_θ^i of agent i , by passing them through a *SoftMax* function. Similarly, we can pool the node scores and calculate a single graph wide value, that will serve as the state value approximation for the Critic network.

The input of a standard GCN [8] layer is the node features $h_{u \in G}^{in}$ for a given graph G and its output is new representative vectors $h_{u \in G}^{out}$ that merge the features of neighboring nodes N , through the convolution operation. This process is repeated to include features from farther neighbors, iteratively producing structure aware node representations h_u^k . The produced representation for node u at the k -th layer of the GCN is provided below, where deg denotes the nodes' degree.

$$h_u^k = \sum_{u' \in N_u} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\deg(u)}\sqrt{\deg(u')}} W \cdot h_{u'}^{k-1} \quad (9)$$

We first input the dependency and requirement graph G^a of current task a through a k -layered GCN to produce a set of node vectors $h_{G^a}^k$, which are then passed through a *MaxPool* function and concatenated with the other domain agents' messages $\omega_{i \in D - \{i\}}$. Messages are vectors of size 3 containing the number of pending domain requests, the average subtask computing requirement c_m , as well as the total percentage of utilization across all nodes in g_i per domain i . Hence, a final representative vector v is calculated for the workload:

Fig. 2: The proposed RL architecture and modified Graph Attention head for the Actor and Critic networks.

$$v = \text{MaxPool}(h_{G_a}^k) \oplus \omega_{i \in D - \{i\}} \quad (10)$$

A GCN that interprets only the infrastructure graph alone and without incorporating peers’ context or the current task’s characteristics would be naive when selecting a suitable node. Inspired by the architecture of GATs, which weigh each neighbor’s importance to each node individually, we employ a graph attention head, to create a modified GNN architecture whose input is the infrastructure node characteristics as well as the workload vector v . Specifically, we introduce an attention head after an f -layered GCN, once the infrastructure graph has been processed to yield the node representations $h_{u \in G_i}^f$. We then update the representations using an attention co-efficient φ , so each node can attend to the vector v with different levels of importance to produce the final logits:

$$h_u^{att} = \varphi_u \cdot h_u^f \quad (11)$$

The coefficients are calculated using the GAT attention head formula, that combines the GCN’s output node scores with the workload context vector v , passing it through a linear transformation and an activation function and normalizing with *SoftMax* for the final result:

$$\varphi_u = \text{SoftMax}\left(\text{LeakyReLU}\left(W\left(h_u^{f-1} \oplus v\right)\right)\right) \quad (12)$$

where W is a linear transformation, rendering the attention head trainable. The final output of the proposed architecture, shown in Fig. 2 along with modified attention head process, comprises infrastructure node logits. Those are calculated based on node and neighborhood features, and the serviced workload and are used to produce either the policy probability distribution or the state value function for the Actor and Critic networks respectively. The Actor converts the logits into a policy distribution π using the *SoftMax* function, from which an action is drawn to interact with the environment and receive a reward, transitioning the agent to a new state. In contrast, the centralized Critic uses global infrastructure and workload telemetry to estimate the state value by pooling all nodes’ logits, providing global insights that convey the Actors’ actions overall effect for efficient training based on CTDE.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

For our simulations, we considered an infrastructure divided into 4 domains, with 40 proprietary nodes split equally among them, and 5 shared nodes available to all schedulers. Specific node characteristics, including computing and bandwidth capacity, power consumption, and device speed are based on real world devices and provided in TABLE I. A total time frame of 10000 periods was considered, each lasting one 10ms. We tested the real-world applicability of our method using the Alibaba Trace 2018 [23], a dataset which contains sampled traces from a production cluster over a period of 8 days. Specifically, we employed the DAG workloads included, as those comprise jobs with dependent subtasks, consistent with our formulation. For each request submitted to the domain orchestrators, we produce the CPU and data processing requirement, as well as the dependency graph, by randomly sampling the extracted jobs and utilizing their characteristics accordingly. Finally, we make comparisons with two baselines, specifically a standard best-fit heuristic and a Multi Agent Deep Q-Network (DQN) scheduler sharing

observation and action spaces, as well as the reward function with our Graph Reinforcement Learning (GRL) scheduler.

TABLE I. NODE CHARACTERISTICS

Type	Proprietary	Shared
Multitude	40 (Total)	5
Based On	Jetson Orin/ Raspberry Pi 4B	Intel Xeon
CPU Cores	4	24
Power Consumption (Watts)	6/15	65
Device Speed	1.2/1.4	2.5
B/W Capacity (bits/sec)	100	1000

B. Experimental Results

Initially, we tested the scheduling performance of the proposed GRL method, by measuring the average achieved end-to-end task execution time (makespan) and energy consumption. Both objectives were weighted equally in the reward function for a balanced performance. The trace was sampled to extract subtraces with different average numbers of total subtasks per task, to assess our method’s ability to handle various degrees of complexity in incoming requests. We trained models with both small and large workloads, respectively denoted as GRL-sw and GRL-lw. The results presented in Fig. 3 showcase limited improvement for small workloads (≤ 5 subtasks) in terms of makespan. As the number of subtasks and dependencies increases, the baselines struggle to interpret the complex spatial graph relations. Our scheduler tackles that issue using the described attention mechanism to produce long term scheduling strategies, with the specialized version decreasing makespan by 22% compared to the baselines. Similarly, the gains in energy consumption increase with the number of subtasks as well. We also notice that both GRL schedulers perform similarly in both metrics with little overfitting, showcasing our method’s generalizability.

To interpret the decreased makespan, assess our method’s assignment choices and test its ability to adapt to greater workload volumes, we measure the parallelization ratio, i.e. the ratio of total processing and propagation time of all subtasks divided by the actual makespan, and collocation ratio, i.e. the percentage of subtasks scheduled at the same node as some predecessor. Experiments conducted with increasing task arrival rates (Fig. 4) show increased collocation compared to baselines by up to 30%, meaning our scheduler retains its ability even in intense workload scenarios with low resource availability. While GRL’s parallelization ratio is similar to the baselines’, it can be attributed to the high collocation degree, which reduces data transfers and thus the ratio’s numerator.

Finally, we test the proposed method’s ability to cooperate and share the available resources. We measure the number of congestion events, meaning the number of times a scheduler attempted to use shared resources and was rejected or delayed, combined with the percentage of subtasks scheduled at proprietary and shared resources. Results presented in Fig. 5 show decreased congestion events by 92% and 86% compared to the heuristic and DQN respectively, thereby showcasing smooth inter domain cooperation. The GRL scheduler manages the attained performance increases by carefully selecting when the powerful shared resources are required as

opposed to the proximal and reliable proprietary ones, made evident by the high degree of proprietary resource preference.

Fig. 3: Task makespan and energy consumption with respect to the average number of subtasks in the workload.

Fig. 4: Parallelism and collocation for various request arrival rates.

Fig. 5: Congestion events and preferred allocation per scheduler.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we proposed a MARL framework for DAG task scheduling in collaborative edge infrastructures. Our approach captures the temporal and logical dependencies of interconnected subtasks, and the spatial relations between computing nodes, by employing a novel GAT modification and standard GCNs, to create specialized, communicating agents, enabling efficient scheduling and cooperative resource allocation with partial environment observability. The applicability of our method is validated by experiments on workloads from the Alibaba 2018 trace, and a configuration based on real devices. Significant improvement over heuristic and DQN methods was demonstrated with decreases in task makespan and shared resource congestion of up to 22% and 92% respectively. The proposed GNN modification proved to be highly resilient to task complexity, highlighting its potential to supplement Actor-Critic architectures and provide effective scheduling in collaborative, distributed infrastructures through a unified MARL and GNN framework.

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